

GENETIC DIVERSITY OF 'CANDIDATUS LIBERIBACTER SOLANACEARUM' DETECTED IN CARROTS, PARSNIP AND PSYLLIDS IN SOUTHWESTERN FRANCE

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Carrot proliferation associated with phloem-limited bacteria transmitted by carrot psyllids was recorded in France in the 1970s (Giannotti et al., 1974). 'Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum' (CaLsol) of different ribosomal haplotypes have recently been associated with carrot disorders in several European countries. In order to reassess disease impact and characterize the CaLsol strains associated, three carrot production areas of Southwestern France were surveyed for CaLsol in 2016. CaLsol could be detected by Taqman real-time PCR (Teresani et al., 2014) in carrots exhibiting stem proliferation and stunting as it was previously reported in Czech Republic (Franova et al., 2000), as well as parsnip and parsley. The disease had a low to moderate incidence in 2 organic carrot fields but was absent in 3 other fields surveyed. Two ribosomal haplotypes could be characterized: a first haplotype D2 differing to the haplotype D by two SNPs in the 16S rDNA and in the 16S-23S spacer sequence and a second corresponding to the haplotype E. Genotyping using the five most variable gene markers described by Glynn and collaborators (2012) showed that haplotypes D2 and E differed for all five markers *dnaG*, *metG*, *recA*, *mutS* and *adk*. *mutS* being the most discriminant with 8 SNPs between haplotype D2 and E. Both haplotypes were detected in carrot and parsnip as well as in *Triozidae* psyllids. The preliminary identification of infected psyllids as *Bactericera trigonica* requires further confirmation.